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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MICROSPONGES
LOADED TOPICAL HYDROGEL FOR THE TREATMENT OF
PLAQUE PSORIASIS.****¹Rupeshri.R. Netkar*, ²Dr.V.P. Wankhade, ³Dr.S.C. Atram, ⁴Dr.N.N. Bobade,
⁵Dr.S.D. Pande.**Student¹, Associated Professor², Associated Professor³, Associated Professor⁴, Principal⁵.
Department of Pharmaceutics, Vidyabharati College of Pharmacy, Amravati 444602, India.**Abstract:**

Microsponge-based drug delivery systems represent an innovative approach to enhance the efficacy and safety of pharmaceutical formulations. This study explores the development and evaluation of clobetasol-loaded microsponges incorporated into a hydrogel matrix for topical application in treating dermatological conditions such as psoriasis. The research optimized microsponge formulations using Eudragit S100 and RS100 polymers, investigating key parameters including drug-polymer ratios, particle size distribution, drug entrapment efficiency, and in vitro drug release profiles. The optimized microsponges exhibited improved stability and sustained release characteristics when integrated into the hydrogel, ensuring prolonged drug delivery and minimized local side effects. Accelerated stability studies confirmed the robustness of the microsponges in maintaining physical integrity and drug content over 30 days under various storage conditions. This study underscores the potential of microsponge technology to revolutionize topical drug delivery, offering controlled release and enhanced therapeutic outcomes for dermatological applications. Future research directions include exploring additional therapeutic agents and optimizing formulations for broader clinical applications.

Keywords: Microsponge technology, Clobetasol, Hydrogel formulation, Dermatological applications, Sustained release, Drug-polymer ratios, Eudragit S100, RS100 polymers, Drug stability.

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INTRODUCTION:

The novel drug delivery systems have been increasingly investigated to achieve targeted and controlled release of drugs as many of conventional delivery systems require high concentrations of active agents to be incorporated for effective therapy because of their low efficiency as delivery systems. Microsponges are highly cross-linked, patented, porous, polymeric microspheres that acquire the flexibility to entrap a wide variety of active ingredients that are mostly used for prolonged topical administration and recently for oral administration. Microsponges are designed to deliver a pharmaceutically active ingredient efficiently at minimum dose and also to enhance stability, elegance, flexibility in formulation, reduce side effects and modify drug release profile.

High potency di halogenated corticosteroid, Clobetasol is used for skin diseases such as vitiligo, psoriasis and atopic dermatitis due to its anti-inflammatory, vasoconstrictive, antiproliferative and immunosuppressive activities. It has been approved for the topical use in dosage forms like such as gel, cream, ointment, solution and foam. Clobetasol is used to relieve redness, itching, swelling, or other discomfort caused by skin conditions. The treatment of more severe skin disorders using Clobetasol with or without the inclusion of other drug substances were compared in several clinical studies. Clobetasol has demonstrated excellent recovery, rapid relief and reduced relapses of different skin conditions and symptoms. It was also proven to be the first topical corticosteroid that demonstrated satisfactory results in the treatment for psoriasis.

The microsphere system can prevent excessive accumulation of ingredients within the epidermis and the dermis. These products are typically presented to the consumer in conventional forms like creams, gels or lotions and they contain relatively high concentration of active ingredients. Microsponges are polymeric delivery systems consisting of porous microspheres that can entrap a wide range of active ingredients such as emollients, fragrances, essential oils, sunscreens, and anti-infective. There have been concerns related to the conventional topical dosage forms such as lotions, creams, ointments and powder

in terms of drug diffusion or release from the vehicle and delivery through the skin.

The primary objective of this research was to produce a topical formulation of clobetasol via using microsphere technology to control the drug delivery and consequently decrease the clobetasol local size effects. Microsponges were prepared by changing several factors to highlight the effect of many formulation variables on the microencapsulation efficiency. Taking into consideration the need for obtaining an aesthetic product, the optimized microsponges formula was intended to have a particle size no larger than 5-300 μm (to prevent any rough sensation) and to be incorporated into vehicle base like aqueous Carbopol 940 hydrogel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

Clobetasol was procured from biunique Pharmaceutical Ltd, India Eudragit S-100; Eudragit RS -100 was obtained from Evonik India Pvt.Ltd, Mumbai. Carbapol-940 and polyvinyl Alcohol was purchased from S D fine chem. Ltd, Mumbai respectively. All other reagents used were of analytical grade. The microsponges were prepared by the quasiemulsion solvent diffusion method.

Method:

The microsponges of respective composition, as shown in table 1, were designed using Eudragit S-100, Eudragit RS-100 as a polymer, and polyvinyl alcohol as a stabilizer. Batches were designed for a different drug: polymer ratios and for different concentrations of polyvinyl alcohol at stirring speed of 1500 rpm. The microsponges containing Clobetasol were prepared by a quasiemulsion solvent diffusion method using Eudragit S-100, Eudragit RS-100 as a polymer. To prepare the inner phase, the polymer is added to ethyl alcohol and the drug is added to methyl alcohol. Polymer solution and drug solution dissolved under ultra-sonication at 35 °C. This solution made inner phase. The inner phase was poured into the PVA solution in water (external phase). Following 2 h stirring at 1500 rpm, the mixture is filtered to separate the microsponges. The microsponges are dried in an air heated oven at 40 °C for 12 h and weighed to determine production yield (PY) (Tab.1.)

Table No 1: list of the ingredients used in formula in different composition in microsponges.

SR. NO.	INGREDIENTS (mg)	FORMULATION CODE							
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Clobetasol (mg)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
2	Eudragit S-100 (mg)	500	1000	500	1000	500	1000	500	1000
3	Eudragit RS-100 (mg)	400	900	900	400	400	900	900	400
4	Ethanol(ml)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
5	Methanol(ml)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
6	PVA %w/v	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
7	Distilled Water(ml)	upto100	upto100	upto100	upto100	upto100	upto100	upto100	upto100

EVALUATION OF CLOBETASOL MICROSPONGES

A. Microscopy: Motic digital microscopy for morphology and surface topography, prepared microsponges can be placed on a glass slide at room temperature and then the surface morphology of the microsponges can be studied by Motic Digital Microscopy (B1 advanced series). Motic Digital Microscopy of a fractured micro sponge particle can also be taken to illustrate its ultrastructure. The morphology of Clobetasol micro sponge was examined with a Motic Digital Microscopy. The samples were mounted on a glass slide and observed under 10X object with the magnification power 2048 x 1536.

B. % drug content and encapsulation efficiency: A sample of dried microsponges equivalent to 10 mg was taken into mortar and pestle and add little amount of phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 and allowed to stand for 24 h. Then transfer content into 100 ml volumetric flask and make up volume to 100 ml with phosphate buffer of pH 7.4. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper (No.41). From the resulting solution take 1ml into 10 ml volumetric flask and then make up volume to 10 ml with phosphate buffer of pH 1.4. Drug content was determined by UV spectrophotometer (Dynamica, Halo DB-20) at 239.

Entrapment efficiency = $\frac{\text{Wt. of total drug} - \text{Wt. of free drug}}{\text{Wt. of total drug}} \times 100$

The drug content and encapsulation efficiency were calculated using the following formula.

$\% \text{Encapsulation Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Actual drug content in Microsponge}}{\text{Theoretical drug content}} \times 100$

$\% \text{ drug content} = \frac{\text{Nact}}{\text{Nms}} \times 100$

Where Nact is the actual Clobetasol content in weighed quantity of microsponges, Nms is the weighed quantity of powder of microsponges.

C. Particle size analysis:

Particle size analysis of prepared microsponges was carried out by using Motic digital microscope particle size analyzer [B1] advanced series. Microsponges were dispersed on the slide before running the sample in the instrument, to ensure that the light scattering signal, particle size was measured, which is within instrument's sensitivity range.

D. Zeta potential:

Zeta potential is an indicator of particle surface charge and particle stability. Particles will not adhere to each other if the value of zeta potential is above +30 or below -30 mV. Zeta size A Zetasizer was used to

determine the particle size distribution of the given samples.

Malvern software was used to analyze the intensity distribution data of particles of different size ranges, and a graphical representation was obtained. The peak on the graph indicates the size of most particles present in the sample.

E. X-ray diffraction (XRD):

XRD analysis of pure drug, polymer and formulation of Clobetasol containing microsponges was conducted to evaluate the nature of drug particles alone as well as in the form of formulated microsponges.

F. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC):

Thermal analysis is an important evaluation technique to find any possible interaction between the drug and excipients. Such interaction can be identified by any change in the thermogram. Thermogram of Clobetasol micro sponge formulation was obtained using DSC instrument (PerkinElmer 4000) equipped with an intercooler. Indium standard was used to calibrate the DSC temperature and enthalpy scale. The powder sample of microsponges was hermetically kept in the Aluminium pan and heated at a constant rate of 10 °C/min, over a temperature range of 30°C to 300°C under a nitrogen atmosphere of the flow rate of 20 ml/min.

Preparation of Clobetasol Microsponge Hydrogel

A gel of Clobetasol micro sponge was prepared using under the moderate stirring, Carbopol 934 was added to a mixture of water and glycerine. Parabens were dissolved in water and mixed with the prior mixture. After that, this mixture was neutralized by adding triethanolamine with gentle mixing. Finally, Clobetasol microsponges (equivalent to 0.1% w/w of Clobetasol) were incorporated to obtain homogenous Clobetasol micro sponge-loaded hydrogels. (Table no.2).

Table No 2: Displays Clobetasol micro sponge gel compositions.

SR.NO.	Ingredients	F4 Microsponges Hydrogel
1	Microsponges (mg)	50
2	Carbopol 940 (g)	0.35
3	Triethanolamine	5ml
4	Methyl Paraben (g)	q.s.
5	PEG-400 (ml)	15ml
6	Distilled Water (ml)	65ml

Evaluation of clobetasol hydrogel

A. Visual inspection:

The prepared hydrogel formulation of microsponges was inspected visually for their colour, texture and appearance.

B. PH measurement:

The PH of hydrogel formulation was determined by using digital pH meter. One gram of hydrogel was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water and stored for two hours. The measurement of pH of the formulation was done.

C. Spreadability studies:

One of the criteria for a hydrogel to meet the ideal qualities is that it should possess good spreadability. It is the term expressed to denote the extent of the area to which hydrogel readily spreads on application the Skin or affected part. The therapeutic efficacy of a formulation also depends upon its spreading value. Spreadability is expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two slides to slip off from hydrogel placed in between the slides under the direction of certain load. Lesser the time is taken for separation of two slides, better the Spreadability. Spreadability was determined by glass slides and a wooden block, which was provided by a pulley at one end. By this method, spreadability was measured on the basis of Slip and Drag characteristics of gels. A ground glass slide was fixed on this block.

An excess of hydrogel (about 1 gm) of different formulations was placed on the ground slide. The hydrogel was then sandwiched between this slide and another glass slide having the dimension of fixed ground slide. Excess of the hydrogel was scrapped off from the edges. The top plate was then subjected to pull of 20 Gms, lesser the time is taken for separation of two slides better the spreadability. Spreadability was then calculated using the following formula:

$$i. S = M \times L / T$$

Where, S is the spreadability, M length moved by the glass slide T is the weight in the pan (tied to the upper slide), L = is the represents the time taken to separate the slide completely from each other.

D. Viscosity measurement:

The viscosity of the different hydrogel formulations was determined using a Brookfield viscometer with spindle no. 4 at 100 rpm at temperature 25°C. The viscosity of the optimized formulation determined as such without dilution using Brookfield Viscometer (Model-LVDV-E). Brookfield Viscometer consists of a cup, which is stationary and a spindle which is rotating. Different sized rotating spindles are used and immersed in the test material. with low viscosity, large size spindles (large diameter and surface area) are used while the higher viscosity liquids small spindles (small

diameter and surface area) are used. Rotate the microspunge hydrogel till I we get a constant dial reading on the display of the viscometer. is repeated three times for reproducible results.

E. Drug content:

1gm of clobetasol microspunge hydrogel was accurately weighed and dissolve using methanol, sonicated for a period 4of 10-15 min and made up to the mark in 100 ml volumetric flask with methanol. From this 10 ml was pipetted out and diluted to 100 ml with methanol and the final dilution was made using distilled water to get a concentration within Beer's range. The substance was measured by UV spectrophotometer (Dynamica, Halo DB-20) at 239 nm against Blank gel treated in the same manner as a sample.

F. In vitro drug diffusion tests:

A vertical Franz diffusion cell with a reservoir capacity of 9.5 mL. was used for in vitro release investigations. Between the compartments of the diffusion cell, a cellulose nitrate membrane with at effective diffusion area of 2.54 cm² was inserted. The receptor medium was composed of a mixture of water and ethanol (50:50, v/v), and it was kept at 32±0.1 °C and swirled constantly. Each formulation weighing 0.5 g of microspunge-based hydrogel was placed on the donor side. 2 mL of the sample was taken from the receiver fluid and replaced with an equal volume of fresh receptor fluid at predefined time intervals. Collected samples were assayed by a 239 UV-Vis spectrophotometer after a suitable dilution.

G. Kinetic study:

To determine the drug release mechanism and to compare the release profile differences among microspunge gel formulations, the data obtained from the drug released amount and time were used. The drug release kinetics was analyzed with mathematical models like Zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix, and Hixson Crowell and Korsmeyer-peppas model. Several kinetic models have been proposed to describe the release characteristics of a drug from the matrix. The three parameters were used to study the release mechanism i.e., release rate constant (k), correlation coefficient (R), and release exponent (n) and determine the best fit model for optimized formulation. The release data was analyzed with the following mathematical models:

H. Zero order kinetics:

Drug dissolution from pharmaceutical dosage forms that do not disaggregate and release the drug slowly (assuming that area does not change and no

equilibrium conditions are obtained) can be presented by the following equation:

$$Q=K_0t. \text{ Eqn (1)}$$

Where, Q is the amount of drug released at time t. K_0 is the zero-order rate constant expressed in units of concentration/time and t-is the time in hours. The pharmaceutical dosage forms following this profile release the same amount of drug by a unit of time. This model represents an ideal release profile in order to achieve the prolonged pharmacological action.

I. First order kinetics:

This model has also be used to describe absorption and/or elimination of some drugs, although it is difficult to conceptualize this mechanism on a theoretical basis.

$$Q_1=Q_e-K_1 t \text{ or } \text{Log } Q_1=\text{Log } Q_0+ K_1 t \text{ Eqn (2)}$$

Where Q_1 is the amount of drug released in time t, Q_0 is the initial amount of drug in the solution and K_1 is the first order release constant. The pharmaceutical dosage form following this dissolution profile, such as water-soluble drugs in porous matrices releases the drug in such a way that is proportional to the amount of drug remaining in its interior, in such a way that the amount of drug released by a unit of time diminishes.

J. Higuchi matrix model:

This model is used to study the release of water soluble and low soluble drugs incorporated in semisolid and/or solid matrices. Mathematical expressions were obtained for drug particles dispersed in a uniform matrix behaving as the diffusion media. It describes drug release as a diffusion process based on the Fick's law, square root time dependent.

$$Q=KH t^{1/2} \text{ Eqn (3)}$$

Where Q is the amount of drug release in time t, KH is the Higuchi dissolution constant.

K. Korsmeyer-peppas model:

Korsmeyer developed a simple, empirical model, relating exponentially the drug release to the elapsed time (t).

$$Ft=a. t^n \text{ Eqn (4)}$$

Where a is a constant incorporating structural and geometric characteristics of the drug dosage form, n is the release exponent, indicative of the drug release mechanism and function of t is M_t/M_0 (fractional release of drug).

L. Hixson-Crowell model:

Hixson and Crowell (1931) recognized that the particles regular area is proportional to the cube root of its volume. They derived the equation:

$$W_0^{1/3}-W_t^{1/3}=k t \text{ Eqn (5)}$$

Where W_0 is the initial amount of drug in the pharmaceutical dosage form, W_t is the remaining amount of drug in the pharmaceutical dosage form at time t and x (κ) is a constant incorporating the surface volume relation. The equation describes the release from systems where there is a change in surface area and diameter of particles or tablets. To study the release kinetics, data obtained from in vitro drug release studies were plotted as the cube root of drug percentage remaining in matrix versus time.

M. Stability testing: Formulation F4 was subjected to stability studies according to ICH guidelines. The formulations were monitored for up to 6 months at $40 \pm 2^\circ/75 \pm 5\%$. At 1,2,3,4, 5 and 6 months, the appearance, pH, viscosity, drug content, and drug release of the hydrogel were evaluated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Preformulation Studies:

A. Conformation of Pure Drug: The received sample of drug Clobetasol was Standardized by carrying out the following tests.

i. Description:

The Clobetasol sample was evaluated visually for appearance and Characteristics of Clobetasol and it confirms that the Colour, Odour, and physical state at a room temperature condition observed for the sample obtained were the same as that of the specification mentioned in the COA.

Table No 3: Physical appearance and characterisation of clobetasol in room temperature.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Specification as per COA	Observation
1	Physical state	Crystalline	Crystalline
2	Colour	White to cream	White to cream
3	Odour	Fruit like breath	Fruit like breath

ii. Solubility Study:

Solubility of Clobetasol in various organic solvents the solubility of Clobetasol was determined in presence of various organic solvents such as DMSO, Methanol, Ethanol and water. Excess amount of Clobetasol was added into the solvents and all the samples were shaken for four hours using a mechanical water bath shaker. All the samples were filtered and the filtrates after suitable dilution with Ethanol were measured at 239 nm spectrophotometrically.

Table No 4: Solubility of clobetasol in various Organic solvents.

Sr. No.	Solvent	Absorbance	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	Ethanol	0.642	10.98
2	DMSO	0.046	0.56
3	Methanol	0.36	0.75
4	DMF	0.016	0.46
5	DCM	0.548	9.34

Graph No 1: Depicts the solubility graph of clobetasol organic solvents.

iii. Melting point determination: Melting point was measured using capillary tube method. The melting point of the Clobetasol was found to be 193-196 °C.

Sr.No.	Parameter	Specification as per COA	Observation
1	Melting Point	196°C-198°C	197.81°C-199.03°C

iv. Drug and Polymer Preformulation study:

A. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy for Analysis of Drug and Excipients: Compatibility Study of drug with Polymer was performed. All the characteristic peaks of Clobetasol appeared in the Drug and polymer physical mixture spectra indicative of no physical and chemical interactions. This means polymers

are compatible with drug. Results observed can be seen in Graph 7.2 and 7.3.

Graph 2: FTIR Spectrum of Pure API (Clobetasol)

=Table No 5: FTIR spectral interpretation of Clobetasol

Sr. No.	Functional groups	Reported Groups(cm-1)	Observed Groups(cm-1)
1	C=O Stretching	1600-16700	1736.01
2	C=C Stretching	1600-1675	1627.03
3	C-H Stretching	2840-3000	2948.32
4	C-F Stretching	490-620	516.94
5	C-Cl Stretching	490-620	516.94
6	O-H Stretching	3200-3700	3306.13
7	C-O Stretching	1000-1300	1211.35

Graph 3: FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture of API & Excipients.

Table No 6: FTIR spectral interpretation of

Sr. No.	Functional groups	Reported Groups (cm-1)	Observed Groups (cm-1)
1	C-H Stretching	2840-3000	2952.18
2	C=O Stretching	1600-16700	1452.46
3	C-O bending	1000-1300	1266.32
4	O-H Stretching	3200-3700	3302.27
5	C-Cl Stretching	490-620	510.19

B. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):

DSC studies were performed to characterize the solid state of drug and polymers. Further, compatibility between drug and excipients can be evaluated by observing the thermal behavior of compounds such as elimination or appearance of an endothermic or exothermic peak. As per the DSC carried out, a sharp endothermic peak appears at a temperature of 65.94°C, which is in range of its melting point and depicted in the graph 7.4.

Graph 4: DSC of Drug**C. Spectrophotometric method for the estimation of Clobetasol:****a) Determination of λ max of clobetasol in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (5% Methanol):**

The maximum absorbance of the Clobetasol was studied and found to be 239 nm as shown in Graph 7.5. Hence, the wavelength of 239 nm was selected for estimation of drug content and analysis of drug in dissolution media.

Graph 5: UV spectrum of Clobetasol

b) Standard Calibration curve of Clobetasol in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (5%Methanol) at 239 nm:

The UV- Visible spectrophotometric method was used to analyze Clobetasol. The absorbance of the drug in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 with 5% Methanol was measured at 239 nm. The results are given in Table No.10 The Calibration Curve of Clobetasol was as shown in Graph 7.6.

Table No 7: Calibration Data of Clobetasol in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (5% Methanol) at 239 nm

Sr. No.	Concentration (ug/ml)	Absorbance $\pm$ SD
1	0	0 $\pm$ 0.0
2	2	0.076 $\pm$ 0.01
3	4	0.155 $\pm$ 0.03
4	6	0.232 $\pm$ 0.05
5	8	0.300 $\pm$ 0.06
6	10	0.374 $\pm$ 0.07
7	20	0.727 $\pm$ 0.08
8	40	1.425 $\pm$ 0.09

*n=3

Graph 6: Calibration Data of Clobetasol in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (5% Methanol) at 239 nm.**Table No 8: Result showing effect of rotation speed on formulation of microsponges.**

Formulation batches	Rotation (RPM)	Temp in 0C	Time (hours)	Shape
F1	400	40	2	Irregular
F2	600	40	2	Irregular
F3	800	40	2	Irregular
F4	1500	40	2	Spherical
F5	400	40	2	Irregular
F6	600	40	2	Irregular
F7	800	40	2	Irregular
F8	1500	40	2	Irregular

From the above study, the effect of rotation on the microsponges formation process was studied. Effect of Rotation (RPM) and temperature on particle size was studied. The microsponges batches were formulated at various RPM such as 400, 600, 800, 1500, and at 1500 RPM, microsponges found spherical shape as compared to other batches. From the above study, the effect of various Rotation on formulation of Microsponges show Spherical shape in batch 4.

7.1.3 Evaluation Of Microsponges:

Microscopy:

Figure No 1: Microscopic image of Clobetasol Microsponges.

A. Drug content and Encapsulation efficiency: In the study of drug entrapment efficiency, F1 shows 91.95%EE, F2 shows 85.30%EE, F3 shows 93.33%EE, F4 shows 98.97%EE, F5 shows 79.55%EE, F6 shows 87.78%EE, F7 shows 92.88%EE, F8 shows 95.09%EE and Drug content was, F1 shows 77.26%, F2 shows 80.60%, F3 shows 86.47%, F4 shows 98.85, F5 shows 87.56%, F6 shows 86.39%, F7 shows 89.99%, F8 shows 96.78% from this study, The F4 batch was optimized batch. The result of the % Drug entrapment efficiency is shown in table no. the formulation of F1 shows the least drug content about 77.26% and higher drug content was shown by F4 formulation. The result shown in table no 14.

Discussion: In this study of drug entrapment efficiency the drug and polymer were greatly affected. The polymer concentration, decreased the entrapment

efficiency and higher polymer concentration, increased the entrapment efficiency. The entrapment efficiency also depends on the drug: polymer interaction. High solubility of polymer in organic solvent, decreased entrapment efficiency and low solubility of polymer in organic solvent, increased entrapment efficiency.

Determination of production yield: The production yield of all batches was ranged from

61.8±0.18% to 86.2±03.8%. The result shown in table no 14.

Discussion: It was found that production yield was greatly affected by drug: polymer ratio as well as by concentration of polyvinyl alcohol. It was indicated that increasing polymer concentration, increased production yield while increasing polyvinyl alcohol concentration, decreased production yield.

Table No 9: Result of % Yield & Drug Content and Encapsulation Efficiency.

Batch no	Encapsulation efficiency (%)	Drug content (%)	% Production Yield
F1	91.95±0.14%	77.26±0.13%	61.8±0.18%
F2	85.30±0.25%	80.68±0.35%	64.85±0.19%
F3	93.33±0.37%	86.47±0.19%	74.13±0.34%
F4	98.97±0.72%	95.85±0.52%	86.2±03.8%
F5	79.55±0.32%	87.56±0.15%	76.5±0.15%
F6	87.78±0.70%	86.39±0.32%	68.35±0.15%
F7	92.88±0.27%	89.99±0.18%	61.33±0.39%
F8	95.09±0.15%	90.78±0.50%	81.73±0.27%

*n=3

B. Particle size analysis: The particle size clobetasol microsponges formulation are tabulated in Table, the particle size of the microsp sponge was determined by optical microscopy and the microsponges were found to be uniform in size 5-300 μm . The average particle size of all formulations ranges from $20.34 \pm 1.12 \mu\text{m}$ to $70.4 \pm 1.20 \mu\text{m}$ which is in increasing order. The result shown in table no 15.

Discussion: Due to the increase in the concentration of polymer but after certain concentration it was observed that as the ratio of drug to polymer was increased, the particle size decreased. This could

probably be due to the fact that in high drug to polymer ratio, the amount of polymer available per microsp sponge was comparatively less. Probably in high drug-polymer ratios less polymer amounts surround the drug and reducing the thickness of polymer wall and microsponges with smaller size were obtained. By performing the particle size analysis, it is concluded that the formulation has the particle size varies with the concentration of polymer drug ratio. On other hand, the particle size of clobetasol decrease with the increase in PVA concentration.

Table No 10: Result of clobetasol base microsponges particle size and zeta sizer.

Batch	Particle Size (μm)	Zeta potential (Mv)
F1	32.4 ± 1.25	-16.2 ± 0.23
F2	30.3 ± 1.23	-13.4 ± 0.32
F3	20.34 ± 1.12	-18.7 ± 0.53
F4	70.4 ± 1.20	-20.0 ± 0.68
F5	29.7 ± 1.03	-10.5 ± 1.25
F6	26.9 ± 1.25	-8.03 ± 1.43
F7	32.9 ± 1.25	-11.9 ± 0.20
F8	40.2 ± 1.36	-19.2 ± 0.78

Graph No 7: Result of particle size image of F4 formulation

Graph No 8: Result of Graphical presentation of Zeta Potential Distribution.

C. Zeta potential and zetasizer: The zeta potential graph plot showed a peak at -21.1mV , of F4 Formulation which meant that most of the microsp sponge particles in formulation had this charge, showing that the particles had an affinity for each other. Results shown is Graph and Table no 15.

- D. X-ray Diffraction Study:** A clear difference was observed in the diffractograms of pure drug and the prepared formulation of figure. Crystallinity of the pure drug was masked when it was captured in microsponges, indicating that Clobetasol was present in the form of solid solution of drug in excipients. While the diffractograms of clobetasol microsphere shows sharp peaks at 14° , 30° , 76° (2θ) with decreased intensity which indicated decrease in crystalline nature of the microsphere. Results are shown in the graph 7.9.

Graph No 9: X-Ray diffraction spectra of pure drug (clobetasol).

Graph No 10: X-ray diffraction spectra of F4 microsphere Formulation.

7.1.3 EVALUATION OF CLOBETASOL MICROSPONGE HYDROGEL:

A. Evaluation of Carbopol 940 hydrogel:

Table No 11: Hydrogel Evaluation.

Sr. No.	Carbopol-940 (mg)	Microsponges (mg)	Ethanol (ml)	PEG-400 (ml)	Ethanolamine (ml)
1	35%	500	15	10	5

From the above study, at the concentration of Carbopol 940 such as 35%. Shows better viscosity and spreadability of Carbopol 940 hydrogel in 35% as best formulation. So that Carbopol 940 polymer was optimized for the preparation of hydrogel Carbopol 940 is an extremely efficient rheology modifier capable of providing high viscosity and forms sparkling clear hydrogel, so that the Carbopol 940 (in 35%) was optimized for microsponges hydrogel preparation.

B. Evaluation Of Clobetasol Microsponge Hydrogel:

- 1. Visual Inspection:** The prepared hydrogel formulations of Clobetasol microsponges were inspected visually for their colour, texture, and appearance. All prepared formulations were pearl white, viscous preparations with a smooth texture and showed in the table no 17.
- 2. pH measurement:** The pH value of all prepared formulations was found to be in the range of 4.03 ± 5.93 , which was considered to be acceptable to avoid the risk of irritation upon application to the skin. Results are shown in the table no 17.
Discussion: The pH of all the formulations was found to be satisfactory in the range of 4.03 ± 5.3 as depicted in the table. The more hydrogen ions present, the lower the pH, conversely the fewer hydrogen ions, the higher the pH.
- 3. Spreadability Study:** The values of spreadability indicated that the hydrogel was easily spreadable by a small amount of shear. Spreadability of micro sponge gel (MGI) was found to be 35.7 g Cm/sec ; indicating that spreadability of drug loaded micro sponge hydrogel was good. Result is shown in the table no 17.
Discussion: In the formulation the F4 batch spreadability is good. The lower the viscosity, then greater its spreadability, and the higher the viscosity, then lower its spreadability.
- 4. Viscosity Studies:** The viscosities studies for micro sponge formulations were carried out. The viscosities of all formulations are shown in table. from above result, micro sponge hydrogel (MGI) has required viscosity. Results are shown in the table no 17. **Discussion:** Viscosity is an expression of the resistance of a fluid. Higher the resistance, then greater the viscosity, and lower the resistance, then lower the viscosity. The resistance offered by fluid to flow freely.
- 5. Drug Content Studies:** Drug content studies for micro sponge formulations were carried out. Drug content of F4 formulations is shown in table the drug content of the formulation showed that the drug was uniformly distributed in the hydrogels. From above result, micro sponge gel (MGI) has higher drug content i.e., 99.31%. Results are shown in the table no 17.

Table No 12: Results of microsponges hydrogel visual inspection pH, Spreadability, Viscosity, %Drug Content.

Formulation of MS hydrogel	Visual Inspection	pH	Spreadability	Viscosity	Drug Content (%)
MG4	Pearl white	4.03 ± 5.3	35.71 ± 4.32	4563.9 ± 2.6	99.32 ± 0.04
MG8	Pearl White	3.6 ± 0.06	27.5 ± 2.36	3227.2 ± 1.62	94.5 ± 0.09

*n=3

Rheology Graph of Hydrogel Containing Microsponge:

Graph No 11: Rheology of Hydrogel Containing Microsponges.

In the above graph shows pseudoplastic behavior. A pseudoplastic fluid is a non-Newtonian fluid whose viscosity decreases with increasing shear rate. This property causes pseudoplastic fluids to exhibit lower viscosity at higher shear rates and higher viscosity at lower shear rates. The thixotropy is depends in time-dependent pseudoplastic behaviors.

Table No 13: Result of Rheology.

RP M	Rad/s ec	Shear Rate	Visco sity (mp as) (V1)	Shear Stress (V1)	Visco sity (mp as) (V2)	Shear Stress (V2)	Visco sity (mp as) (V3)	Shear Stress (V3)	Visco sity (mp as) (V4)	Shear Stress (V4)
10	1.047	2.105	20651	0.00010	19611	0.000107	20763	0.0001	20945	0.00010
	20	34		1948		355		014		0518
20	2.094	4.210	13017	0.00032	13719	0.000306	12025	0.0003	90645	0.00004
	40	68		3475		923		5016		6452
30	3.141	6.316	10109	0.00062	6846.5	0.000922	11204	0.0005	10985	0.00057
	59	01		479		516		6373		4967
50	5.235	10.52	7290.6	0.00144	5379.2	0.001956	5299.7	0.0019	4567.5	0.00230
	98	668		387		922		8628		4692
100	10.47	21.05	4563.9	0.00461	3227.2	0.006523	5675.8	0.0037	3664.8	0.00057
	197	338		3023		729		0932		4475
50	5.235	10.52	7124.3	0.00207	5936.1	0.001773	8675.	0.0012	3456.9	0.00304
	98	668		757		3326	4	1339		5121
30	3.141	6.316	10099	0.00035	7764.9	0.000813	10299	0.0006	68745	0.00009
	59	01		5409		4052		1326		1875
20	2.094	4.210	12895	0.00063	7314.4	0.000575	13895	0.0003	13998	0.00030
	40	68		6536		669		0304		0806
10	1.047	2.105	20599	0.00010	9549.5	0.000220	20699	0.0001	20645	0.00010
	20	34		2206		465		017		1978

6. In-Vitro Drug Diffusion study: The cumulative percent drug diffusion for formulation batch MG4. MG4 batch was more than other batches show 98.91% these results are shown in graph.

Table No 14: Result of %CDD of formulation of microsponges.

Sr. No.	Time (hr)	%Cumulative Drug Diffusion							
		MG1	MG2	MG3	MG4	MG5	MG6	MG7	MG8
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	5.25	5.89	9.25	9.84	4.44	3.45	14.47	6.56
2	2	22.24	18.59	16.99	18.54	12.71	8.22	20.65	21.4
3	3	25.31	38.21	20.72	34.49	20.55	15.63	24.78	27.38
4	4	42.37	44.51	38.21	50.91	26.64	28.09	30.33	36.67
5	5	55.17	69.89	64.13	69.47	37.56	45.72	35.87	45.76
6	6	64.77	70.43	76.51	78.64	43.57	68.81	44.56	53.54
7	7	79.71	85.04	82.91	87.17	62.81	78.53	72.25	65.2
8	8	89.31	93.57	95.7	98.91	87.77	83.24	80.06	92.34

Graph No 12: % Cumulative Drug Release. Vs Time (hr).

Discussion: Diffusion of the drug across the epithelial layer largely depends on molecular weight and molecular size of the drug. Very large molecules have lower diffusion than small molecules. Drug diffusion decreases with increase in molecular size.

7. Drug release kinetic study of optimized formulation MGF4:

To determine the kinetic of release, drug diffusion data were treated with different kinetic equations. Obtained drug diffusion data was fitted to Zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix model, Hixson Crowell model, and Korsmeyer-peppas model. The three parameters were used to study the release mechanism i.e. release rate constant (k), correlation coefficient (R), release exponent (n). correlation coefficient (R), release rate constant (k), of optimized formulation F4 (MG4), is reported in table no 21. The model that fits the release data was selected based on the correlation coefficient (R) value in various models. The model that gave the high 'R' value was considered as the best fit of release data. Korsmeyer peppas model best described the sustained release of optimized (MG4) formulation and the diffusion exponent (n) value was found to be 1.16395 suggesting that the Fick's law of diffusion was not followed. From the result, the best fit model for optimized formulation F4 (MG4) is Zero order.

Table No 15: Release Kinetics Of Optimized Formulation (F4) MGF4 Model Formulation Code.

Sr. No.	Model	Formulation Code
1	Zero Order	$R^2 = 0.9949$
2	First Order	$R^2 = 0.7657$
3	Higuchi Matrix	$R^2 = 0.8012$
4	Hixson Crowell	$R^2 = 0.9147$
5	Korsmeyer's Peppas	$R^2 = 0.9884$

8. **Accelerated Stability Study:** The batch F4 was subjected to 3–4-month stability study at accelerated conditions and was analyzed for physical appearance, in vitro drug release and FTIR spectroscopy. After 3-4 months, the formulation was found with no significant change in its appearance. The in vitro percentage drug release came out to be 98.91% similar and also the FTIR spectra revealed no sign of instability. Thus, all these parameters suggested that the formulation F4 may have good shelf life.

Table No 16: Accelerated Stability data for Optimized Formulation-F4

Sr. No.	Parameter	Condition: 40±20C±	
		Initial	After 1 Month
1	Visual appearance	Pearl White	Pearl white
2	Pourability	Easily Pourable	Easily Pourable
3	pH	4.03±0.03	4.03±0.02
4	Gelling capacity	+++	+++
5	Viscosity	4563.9±2.6	4562.8±1.6
6	Drug content	99.32±0.04	99.27±0.12

9. Microscopy:

Figure No 2: Microscopic image of Microsponges loaded Hydrogel.

CONCLUSION:

Microsponges represent a promising avenue in drug delivery technology, offering unique benefits such as sustained release, improved stability, and reduced side effects. This study's focus on clobetasol microsponges hydrogel demonstrates the potential of this delivery system for treating psoriasis and similar dermatological conditions.

The optimized microsphere formulations F4, particularly those prepared with Eudragit S100 (1000mg) and RS100 (400mg) polymers, exhibited efficient sustained drug release profiles. These microsponges, when incorporated into hydrogel, maintained their stability and provided sustained drug release over an extended period, making them more effective than conventional formulations.

The study's findings highlight the importance of careful formulation and evaluation of microsphere-based delivery systems, emphasizing factors such as drug-polymer ratios, preparation methods, and storage conditions. Quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion emerged as a preferred method for microsphere preparation due to its simplicity and efficiency.

Overall, clobetasol microsponges and microsphere hydrogel prepared in this study show promise for improving topical drug delivery, offering enhanced efficacy and patient outcomes compared to conventional therapies. Further research and development in this area can lead to the optimization of microsphere formulations for a wide range of therapeutic applications, thereby advancing drug delivery technology and patient care.

Future Prospects:

A Microsphere consists of a myriad of interconnecting voids with in non-collapsible structure that can accept a wide variety of substance. The outer surface is typically porous allowing the flow of substance into and out of the sphere, scientist are more concentrating on delivery of sunscreen, antidandruff, anti-acne, anti-psoriatic, agents which can also use in delivery of thermo labile substance such as vaccines, proteins, peptides, and DNA based therapeutics. There is alot of scope to encapsulate anti-fungal drugs, anti-cancer drugs, anti-infective drugs, anti-AIDS drugs, anti-inflammatory drugs, anti-viral drugs, etc. In microsponges to use them as promising drug carriers to achieve better bioavailability and targeting properties and for reducing the side- effects of the drugs. Microsponges hydrogel as a promising

approach for enhancing drug bioavailability. We can also do animal study and bioavailability study & Bioequivalence studies with the marketed formulation.

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